

THE MAIN ASPECTS OF THE FORMATION OF PHYSICAL CULTURE IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

Gayrat Goynazarov, lecturer,

Fergana State University, Uzbekistan, Fergana city

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Abstract: Creating a healthy lifestyle in our society, creating modern conditions for regular physical culture and mass sports of the population, especially the younger generation, strengthening confidence in the will, strength and capabilities of young people through sports competitions, courage and patriotism, motherhood Extensive work is being done to develop a sense of devotion to the motherland, as well as the systematic organization of the selection of talented athletes among young people and the further development of physical culture and mass sports.

This article scientifically explores the role and functions of physical culture science in the education system.

Keywords: physical education, physical culture, physical education theory, health, sports, upbringing of a healthy generation, healthy lifestyle, physical education system.

ОСНОВНЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ В ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОМ ПРОЦЕССЕ

Аннотация: Формирование здорового образа жизни в нашем обществе, создание современных условий для регулярной физической культуры и массового спорта населения, особенно подрастающего поколения, укрепление уверенности в воле, силе и возможностях молодежи посредством спортивных соревнований, мужества и патриотизма, материнства Проводится большая работа по развитию чувства преданность Родине, а также системная организация отбора талантливых спортсменов среди молодежи и дальнейшее развитие физической культуры и массового спорта.

В данной статье научно исследуется роль и функции науки о физической культуре в системе образования.

Ключевые слова: физическое воспитание, физическая культура, теория физического воспитания, здоровье, спорт, воспитание здорового поколения, здоровый образ жизни, система физического воспитания.

INTRODUCTION

Historically, the issue of education has been the most pressing issue in society, and today it is one of the main issues. Because the education of the members of the society is the decisive force in the whole existence of the society of its time, that is, its development, well-being, enlightenment and spirituality, economic stability, cooperation of the members of the society, peace in the world, joint solution of various problems is calculated. Physical culture, which is an integral part of such a unique system, has a unique role to play in ensuring the full development and activity of members of society. Taking this into account, special attention is paid to physical culture in our country.

Physical culture is a set of special measures, including the physical development of a person by directing the special means and methods of sports and culture, along with the means of physical education in the comprehensive education of the builders of a new society, mature people. Physical culture is a part of the general culture, the development of which depends on the level of socio-economic development of society.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

The urgent task before us today is to create a unique way of life based on economic, social and political principles. It is understood that an important factor in determining sustainable development in all respects is a healthy lifestyle, a healthy lifestyle, as well as the expansion of the number of young people who regularly engage in sports. It should be noted that there is no doubt that a healthy and long life has always been a dream of mankind. In this regard, the main task of any society is to realize this dream of humanity, that is, to create conditions for the health and longevity of citizens.

In the education system, physical culture is taught as a subject, and this subject has its own set of objectives. The goal of the science of physical culture is to achieve physical maturity, comprehensive education, preparation of them for active participation in a democratic state based on the rule of law, creative work and defense of the Motherland. To achieve this goal, of course, will be achieved through the study of the science of physical culture in the field, the implementation of the data obtained as a result of scientific research in practice and teaching students. In this way, the knowledge, skills and abilities of members of society in the field of physical culture are developed.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

“Today, the development of a healthy lifestyle and physical culture has become a topical issue. Maintaining the status of this type of activity, especially among athletes, is required to form the right opinion among the people. One of the problems studied in the science of psychology is the motive and motivation, on which there are views of the type theories. In particular, local psychologists E.G.Goziev, G.B.Shoumarov, V.Karimova, B.R.Kadyrov, I.M.Mamatov, Russian psychologists K.D.Ushinsky, I.M.Sechenov, I.P.Pavlov, V.M.Bexterev, A.F.Lazurskiy, V.N.Myasishev, A.A.Ukhtomskiy, D.N.Uznadze, S.L.Rubinshteyn, A.N.Leontev, P.M.Yakobson, V.S.Merlin, L.I.Bojovich, V.I.Selivanov, V.G.Aseev and others conducted research on this problem and left their theories” [1, 72].

Definitions given by experts (L.P.Matveev, A.D.Novikov, B.A.Ashmarin, A.S.Kholodov, H.T.Rafiev, A.Abdullaev, R.Abdumalikov), in existing dictionaries and encyclopedias Based on the data, physical culture is an integral part of the general culture. It can be concluded that it covers species.

The concept of innovation is quite diverse and depends mainly on its application. In short, innovation is the successful use of new ideas. Today, the predominant areas of innovation are developments in the areas of energy efficiency, safety, ecology, information technology, and innovation in construction. There are also several main profiles: information and communication technologies, innovative technologies and equipment for the oil and gas and petrochemical industries, industrial automation and intelligent systems, biotechnology, nanotechnology, etc. The introduction of innovative technologies in education requires new approaches to teaching based on modern educational technologies. Modern educational technologies, first of all, should work for creative education, contributing to the creative development of the personality of each student.

The structure of educational technology includes such components as goal-setting, monitoring and evaluation, while the basis of the modern education system is information technology. At the same time, it is essential that innovative technologies in education require not only development, but also the creation of an appropriate information and educational environment. The information-rich living space through the media and the Internet can have both a positive and a negative impact on human consciousness. Various manipulative methods of influence can have a negative impact on the personal

and social strategy of harmonious development. Their influence on the minds of young people is especially dangerous, who, due to their age, are often gullible, naive in a certain sense and are more suggestible. In the modern world, the media are increasingly becoming not just a source of information, but a channel of ideological influence on the consciousness of people. In the arsenal of means of manipulative influence for the purpose of indoctrination and reorientation, there is a huge number of techniques, both well-known and innovative.

The targets of such an impact can be: the social activity of the individual, the style of her thinking and activity, the psychological mood and emotional background of life, worldview foundations.

The goal of physical education is to shape a person's physical maturity, strengthen their health, and increase their ability to work from an early age. The purpose of physical culture in society is to develop all areas of society in conjunction with the development of society, that is, not only the education of the individual, but also all areas of the above areas.

We begin to achieve better results if each of us thinks at least a little about life, life expectancy, life and health. Almost everyone sooner or later has a health problem. Because diseases and accidents are the main cause of death among people, and premature death occurs in almost all cases. A person deprived of health is always left alone in the face of diseases and their terrible consequence – death. One bitter truth in life is that everyone's health is not needed by anyone but himself, and no one cares about it except himself. To a certain extent, parents, children, and close relatives can take care of his health. But even their grief in most cases may not turn into anything other than sympathy and regret.

In many cases, according to the understanding developed by each person in this matter, the main pillar of human health is the available medical service, to which a person turns primarily in case of illness and lives all his life relying on this service. It is quite natural to wonder whether the formulated understanding of anashu is correct or not. Medicine has great potential when it comes to health wishes that are not true. But health is not always and all life can be preserved with the help of medical procedures. This is absolutely impossible.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the above research, the following conclusions can be drawn: The concept of "physical culture", its concepts and terms are historically formed and developed in the language of each nation;

Defining the concepts and terms in the field of "Physical Culture" as an important area of research in Uzbek linguistics;

Physical culture is one of the main factors in the deep integration of the concepts and terms of the field into the daily life of the population, their deep involvement in physical activity through the deepening of their knowledge. In this regard, the educational process in the teaching of physical culture in educational institutions is one of the leading factors. Therefore, it is necessary to develop various dictionaries, annotated dictionaries in the field.

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